

Studies in Heterocyclic Compounds. Part XVIII. Synthesis of 3, 5-diaryl-4-(N-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) pyrazoles as potential antibacterials

(MRS) AJAYA KABRA, G. S. SAHARIA and H. R. SHARMA

Department of Chemistry, University of Delhi, Delhi-110007

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In a search for new antibacterials, some 3-(*m/p*-nitrophenyl)-5-*p*-toluyl-4-(N-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) pyrazoles have been synthesised by condensing 1-(*m/p*-nitrophenyl)-3-*p*-toluyl-2-(N-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) propane-1, 3-diones with a number of carbonyl reagents. On testing *in vitro* against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* encouraging results were obtained.

In a phased programme on the study of the structure-activity relationship amongst the pyrazole derivatives¹, we report here the synthesis and *in vitro* antibacterial activity of some 3-(*m/p*-nitrophenyl)-5-*p*-toluyl-4-(N-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) pyrazoles in order to study the effect of (i) replacing the halogen atom or methoxyl group by a methyl group in the phenyl ring attached at position 5 and (ii) shifting the nitro group from meta to para position in the phenyl ring at position 3 on the antibacterial activity. These compounds were synthesised by condensing 1-(*m/p*-nitrophenyl)-3-*p*-toluyl-2-(N-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) propane-1, 3-diones with hydrazine hydrate (100%), phenylhydrazine, *p*-nitrophenylhydrazine and benzoylhydrazine in presence of glacial acetic acid. The purity and homogeneity of all these compounds was checked by TLC and elemental analysis and the structure assigned on the basis of analogous earlier work².

Experimental

All 1-(*m/p*-nitrophenyl)-3-*p*-toluyl-2-(N-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) propane-1, 3-diones required for this work were synthesised by the method reported earlier.³

Synthesis of 1,3-diaryl-4-(N-substituted p-sulphamylbenzeneazo) pyrazoles

Synthesis of 1,3-di (p-nitrophenyl)-5-p-toluyl-4-(p-sulphamylbenzeneazo) pyrazole.

A mixture of 1-(*p*-nitrophenyl)-3-*p*-toluyl-2-(*p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) propane-1,3-diones (0.1g) and *p*-nitrophenylhydrazine (0.05 g) in glacial acetic acid-ethanol mixture containing 1-2 drops of concentrated sulphuric acid was refluxed in a water bath for 7-8 hrs and then left overnight. The deposited solid was filtered, dried and crystallised from glacial acetic acid-DMF mixture in orange needles, m.p. 268°. (Yield : 0.09 g ; 70%).

(Found : C, 57.7 ; H, 3.7. C₂₈H₂₁O₈N₇S requires C, 57.6 ; H, 3.6%).

Other, 1, 3-di (*p*-nitrophenyl)-5-*p*-toluyl-4-(N-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) pyrazoles were prepared in the manner described above.

The reactions with hydrazine hydrate (100%), phenylhydrazine, and benzoyl hydrazine were carried out by the methods reported earlier.⁴

Similar set of reactions were carried out with 1-(*m*-nitrophenyl)-3-*p*-toluyl-2-(N-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) propane-1, 3-diones.

All the pyrazole derivatives were later subjected to screening *in vitro* against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. On comparing the results of the biological assay with those obtained earlier⁵, it is clear that (a) shifting of the nitro group from meta to the para position in the phenyl ring attached at position-3 of the pyrazole nucleus results in enhancement of the antibacterial activity with only a few exceptions, (b) replacement of the halogen atom in the phenyl ring attached at position-5 of the azole nucleus by a methyl group causes an overall decrease in the activity and this is in confirmation of our results of the screening tests with 3-methyl-5(*p*-alkylphenyl)-4-N-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo pyrazoles⁶. Similar effect was also observed when the methoxyl group attached to the phenyl ring at position-5 was replaced by a methyl group.

All the pyrazole derivatives and the results of their screening are entered in Tables 1-8.

TABLE 1—3-(P-NITROPHENYL)-5-P-TOLUYL-4-(N-SUBSTITUTED P-SULPHAMYL BENZENE AZO) PYRAZOLES

(I: X=p-NO₂; Y=p-CH₃; R₁-H)

S. No.	R	M.P. °C	Colour	Yield %	Molecular Formula	Antibacterial activity <i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
1.	H	> 300	R	74	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₆ S	(-)	(-)
2.	Acetyl	> 300	R	75	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ O ₅ N ₆ S	(-)	(-)
3.	Phenyl	265	SR	75	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₆ S	(-)	(-)
4.	o-Methylphenyl	258	SRN	76	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₆ S	(+)	(+)
5.	o-Methoxyphenyl	232	ON	78	C ₂₉ H ₂₄ O ₅ N ₆ S	(+)	(-)
6.	p-Methoxyphenyl	254	ON	72	C ₂₉ H ₂₄ O ₅ N ₆ S	(+)	(+)
7.	Guanidyl	> 300	SON	73	C ₂₉ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₇ S	(+)	(+)
8.	α-Pyridyl	260	RF	74	C ₂₇ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₇ S	(+)	(-)
9.	Pyrimidyl	> 300	ORN	75	C ₂₉ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₆ S	(++)	(-)
10.	4,6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	246	OR	78	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₆ S	(+)	(+)
11.	2,6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	296	R	70	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₆ S	(++)	(-)
12.	2,6-Dimethoxypyrimidyl	270	SR	73	C ₂₉ H ₂₄ O ₅ N ₆ S	(++)	(+)
13.	5-Methyl-1,3,4-thiadiazolyl	277	SR	75	C ₂₈ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₆ S ₂	(++)	(-)

TABLE 2—1-PHENYL-3-(P-NITROPHENYL)-5-P-TOLUYL-4-(N-SUBSTITUTED P-SULPHAMYL BENZENE AZO) PYRAZOLES.

(I: X=p-NO₂; Y=p-CH₃; R₁=C₆H₅)

S. No.	R	M.P. °C	Colour	Yield %	Molecular formula	Antibacterial activity <i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
1.	H	245	ON	66	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₆ S	(+)	(-)
2.	Acetyl	245	O	65	C ₃₀ H ₂₆ O ₅ N ₆ S	(+)	(-)
3.	Phenyl	252	SOR	65	C ₃₄ H ₂₆ O ₄ N ₆ S	(+)	(++)
4.	o-Methylphenyl	218	R	68	C ₃₄ H ₂₈ O ₄ N ₆ S	(+)	(+)
5.	o-Methoxyphenyl	232	SR	67	C ₃₅ H ₂₈ O ₅ N ₆ S	(+)	(-)
6.	p-Methoxyphenyl	235	O	64	C ₃₅ H ₂₈ O ₅ N ₆ S	(-)	(-)
7.	Guanidyl	198	ON	66	C ₃₅ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₇ S	(+)	(-)
8.	α-Pyridyl	282	SO	70	C ₃₃ H ₂₅ O ₄ N ₇ S	(+)	(+)
9.	Pyrimidyl	> 300	OF	69	C ₃₅ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₆ S	(+)	(+)
10.	4,6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	268	OR	65	C ₃₄ H ₂₈ O ₄ N ₆ S	(+)	(+)
11.	2,6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	272	SO	66	C ₃₄ H ₂₈ O ₄ N ₆ S	(-)	(-)
12.	2,6-Dimethoxypyrimidyl	214	OF	70	C ₃₅ H ₂₈ O ₅ N ₆ S	(-)	(-)
13.	5-Methyl-1,3,4-thiadiazolyl	> 300	R	64	C ₃₁ H ₂₆ O ₄ N ₆ S ₂	(+++)	(+)

TABLE 3—1,3-Di(*p*-NITROPHENYL)-5-*p*-TOLUYL-4-(*N*-SUBSTITUTED *p*-SULPHAMYL BENZENEAZO) PYRAZOLES

(I : X = *p*-NO₂ ; Y = *p*-CH₃ ; R₁ = C₆H₄NO₂)

S. No.	R	M.P. °C	Colour	Yield %	Molecular formula	Antibacterial activity	
						<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
1.	H	268	SO	70	C ₂₈ H ₂₁ O ₈ N ₇ S	(++)	(-)
2.	Acetyl	245	SR	68	C ₃₀ H ₂₃ O ₇ N ₇ S	(+)	(-)
3.	Phenyl	203	R	69	C ₃₄ H ₂₅ O ₈ N ₇ S	(-)	(-)
4.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	240	R	72	C ₃₅ H ₂₇ O ₈ N ₇ S	(-)	(+)
5.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	244	RN	70	C ₃₅ H ₂₇ O ₇ N ₇ S	(+)	(++)
6.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	222	SRN	68	C ₃₅ H ₂₇ O ₇ N ₇ S	(-)	(-)
7.	Guanidyl	> 300	R	69	C ₃₉ H ₂₉ O ₈ N ₉ S	(-)	(-)
8.	α -Pyridyl	220	SR	69	C ₃₉ H ₂₉ O ₈ N ₉ S	(-)	(-)
9.	Pyrimidyl	296	SR	70	C ₃₉ H ₂₉ O ₈ N ₉ S	(+)	(+)
10.	4,6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	279	SRN	68	C ₄₄ H ₃₇ O ₈ N ₉ S	(-)	(-)
11.	2,6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	225	OF	67	C ₄₄ H ₃₇ O ₈ N ₉ S	(-)	(-)
12.	2,6-Dimethoxy-pyrimidyl	196	OR	62	C ₄₄ H ₃₇ O ₈ N ₉ S	(+)	(-)
13.	5-Methyl-1,3,4-thiadiazolyl	260	RF	72	C ₄₁ H ₃₁ O ₈ N ₆ S ₂	(++)	(-)

TABLE 4—1-BENZOYL-3-(*p*-NITROPHENYL-5-*p*-TOLUYL)-4-(*N*-SUBSTITUTED *p*-SULPHAMYL BENZENEAZO) PYRAZOLES

(I : X = *p*-NO₂ ; Y = *p*-CH₃ ; R₁ = COC₆H₅)

S. No.	R	M.P. °C	Colour	Yield %	Molecular formula	Antibacterial activity	
						<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
1.	H	> 300	SO	75	C ₂₉ H ₂₂ O ₈ N ₆ S	(+)	(+)
2.	Acetyl	288	O	74	C ₃₁ H ₂₄ O ₈ N ₆ S	(+)	(+)
3.	Phenyl	287	OF	76	C ₃₅ H ₂₆ O ₈ N ₆ S	(-)	(+)
4.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	270	RN	72	C ₃₆ H ₂₈ O ₈ N ₆ S	(+)	(-)
5.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	237	ON	73	C ₃₆ H ₂₈ O ₈ N ₆ S	(+)	(-)
6.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	267	SON	74	C ₃₆ H ₂₈ O ₈ N ₆ S	(-)	(-)
7.	Guanidyl	288	RF	75	C ₄₀ H ₃₀ O ₈ N ₈ S	(+)	(+)
8.	α -Pyridyl	291	O	76	C ₄₀ H ₃₀ O ₈ N ₈ S	(+)	(+)
9.	Pyrimidyl	290	O	75	C ₄₀ H ₃₀ O ₈ N ₈ S	(+)	(+)
10.	4,6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	249	SRN	74	C ₄₅ H ₃₄ O ₈ N ₈ S	(-)	(-)
11.	2,6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	> 300	SRN	72	C ₄₅ H ₃₄ O ₈ N ₈ S	(+)	(-)
12.	2,6-Dimethoxy-pyrimidyl	268	OF	70	C ₄₅ H ₃₄ O ₈ N ₈ S	(++)	(+)
13.	5-Methyl-1,3,4-thiadiazolyl	287	R	74	C ₄₂ H ₃₄ O ₈ N ₆ S ₂	(+++)	(+)

TABLE 5—3-(*m*-NITROPHENYL)-5-*p*-TOLUYL-4-(*N*-SUBSTITUTED *p*-SULPHAMYL BENZENEAZO) PYRAZOLES

(I : X = *m*-NO₂ ; Y = *p*-CH₃ ; R₁ = H)

S. No.	R	M.P. °C	Colour	Yield %	Molecular formula	Antibacterial activity	
						<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
1.	H	288	OF	70	C ₂₉ H ₁₈ O ₈ N ₆ S	(+)	(-)
2.	Acetyl	290	O	74	C ₃₁ H ₂₀ O ₈ N ₆ S	(+)	(-)
3.	Phenyl	237	RN	76	C ₃₅ H ₂₂ O ₈ N ₆ S	(-)	(-)
4.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	223	SRN	72	C ₃₆ H ₂₄ O ₈ N ₆ S	(-)	(+)
5.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	212	OR	78	C ₃₆ H ₂₄ O ₇ N ₆ S	(-)	(+)
6.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	207	O	79	C ₃₆ H ₂₄ O ₈ N ₆ S	(+)	(+)
7.	Guanidyl	294	O	70	C ₄₀ H ₂₆ O ₈ N ₈ S	(+)	(+)
8.	α -Pyridyl	235	R	80	C ₄₀ H ₂₆ O ₈ N ₈ S	(+)	(+)
9.	Pyrimidyl	290	R	80	C ₄₀ H ₂₆ O ₈ N ₈ S	(++)	(-)
10.	4,6-Dimethyl pyrimidyl	180	ON	78	C ₄₅ H ₃₀ O ₈ N ₈ S	(+)	(+)
11.	2,6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	281	SO	78	C ₄₅ H ₃₀ O ₈ N ₈ S	(+)	(+)
12.	2,6-Dimethoxy-pyrimidyl	130	SR	65	C ₄₅ H ₃₀ O ₈ N ₈ S	(+)	(+)
13.	5-Methyl-1,3,4-thiadiazolyl	288	R	72	C ₄₂ H ₃₀ O ₈ N ₆ S ₂	(+++)	(-)

TABLE 6—1-PHENYL-3-(*m*-NITROPHENYL)-5-*p*-TOLUYL-4-(*N*-SUBSTITUTED *p*-SULPHAMYL BENZEAZO) PYRAZOLES

(I : X = *m*-NO₂ ; Y = *p*-CH₃ ; R₁ = C₆H₅)

S. No.	R	M.P. °C	Colour	Yield %	Molecular formula	Antibacterial activity	
						<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
1.	H	224	O	66	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₆ S	(-)	(+)
2.	Acetyl	216	R	65	C ₃₀ H ₂₄ O ₅ N ₆ S	(+)	(-)
3.	Phenyl	242	SR	63	C ₃₄ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₆ S	(+)	(+)
4.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	232	SR	68	C ₂₈ H ₂₈ O ₄ N ₆ S	(+)	(+)
5.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	232	RN	70	C ₂₈ H ₂₈ O ₅ N ₆ S	(-)	(+)
6.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	196	R	67	C ₂₈ H ₂₈ O ₅ N ₆ S	(+)	(-)
7.	Guanidyl	252	OR	69	C ₂₉ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₈ S	(+)	(-)
8.	α -Pyridyl	231	RF	72	C ₂₃ H ₂₅ O ₄ N ₇ S	(-)	(-)
9.	Pyrimidyl	240	R	70	C ₂₃ H ₂₅ O ₄ N ₇ S	(-)	(+)
10.	4,6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	222	SR	68	C ₂₅ H ₂₇ O ₄ N ₈ S	(+)	(+)
11.	2,6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	150	O	64	C ₂₄ H ₂₈ O ₄ N ₈ S	(+)	(+)
12.	2,6-Dimethoxypyrimidyl	262	OF	67	C ₂₄ H ₂₈ O ₆ N ₈ S	(++)	(+)
13.	5-Methyl-1,3,4-thiadiazolyl	160	R	66	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₈ S ₂	(+++)	(+)

TABLE 7—1(*p*-NITROPHENYL)-3-(*m*-NITROPHENYL)-5-*p*-TOLUYL 4-(*N*-SUBSTITUTED *p*-SULPHAMYL BENZEAZO)PYRAZOLES

(I : X = *m*-NO₂ ; Y = *p*-CH₃ ; R₁ = C₆H₄NO₂)

S. No.	R	M.P. °C	Colour	Yield %	Molecular formula	Antibacterial activity	
						<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
1.	H	298	R	72	C ₃₈ H ₂₁ O ₆ N ₇ S	(-)	(-)
2.	Acetyl	297	RN	71	C ₄₀ H ₂₃ O ₇ N ₇ S	(-)	(+)
3.	Phenyl	214	SR	67	C ₄₄ H ₂₅ O ₆ N ₇ S	(+)	(++)
4.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	210	DR	60	C ₃₈ H ₂₉ O ₆ N ₇ S	(+)	(+)
5.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	220	O	61	C ₃₈ H ₂₉ O ₇ N ₇ S	(-)	(-)
6.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	228	O	64	C ₃₈ H ₂₉ O ₇ N ₇ S	(-)	(-)
7.	Guanidyl	195	O	60	C ₃₉ H ₂₅ O ₆ N ₉ S	(+)	(-)
8.	α -Pyridyl	272	OR	66	C ₃₃ H ₂₄ O ₆ N ₈ S	(-)	(++)
9.	Pyrimidyl	> 300	DR	62	C ₃₃ H ₂₄ O ₆ N ₈ S	(-)	(+)
10.	4,6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	> 300	R	63	C ₃₅ H ₂₆ O ₆ N ₉ S	(+)	(+)
11.	5-Methyl-1,3,4-thiadiazolyl	284	R	65	C ₃₁ H ₂₁ O ₆ N ₉ S ₂	(+++)	(++)

TABLE 8—1-BENZOYL-3-(*m*-NITROPHENYL)-5-*p*-TOLUYL-4-(*N*-SUBSTITUTED *p*-SULPHAMYL BENZEAZO) PYRAZOLES

(I : X = *m*-NO₂ ; Y = *p*-CH₃, R₁ = COC₆H₅)

S. No.	R	M.P. °C	Colour	Yield %	Molecular formula	Antibacterial activity	
						<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
1.	H	295	OF	76	C ₃₉ H ₂₃ O ₆ N ₆ S	(+)	(-)
2.	Acetyl	294	O	75	C ₄₁ H ₂₅ O ₇ N ₆ S	(-)	(-)
3.	Phenyl	218	O	74	C ₄₅ H ₂₅ O ₆ N ₆ S	(-)	(-)
4.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	221	R	75	C ₃₉ H ₂₉ O ₆ N ₆ S	(+)	(+)
5.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	> 300	ON	72	C ₃₉ H ₂₉ O ₇ N ₆ S	(+)	(-)
6.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	209	ON	70	C ₃₉ H ₂₉ O ₇ N ₆ S	(-)	(-)
7.	Guanidyl	298	R	74	C ₄₀ H ₂₅ O ₆ N ₈ S	(-)	(+)
8.	α -Pyridyl	240	R	70	C ₃₄ H ₂₅ O ₆ N ₇ S	(+)	(+)
9.	Pyrimidyl	261	O	72	C ₃₄ H ₂₅ O ₆ N ₇ S	(++)	(+)
10.	4,6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	269	RN	74	C ₃₆ H ₂₇ O ₆ N ₈ S	(+)	(+)
11.	2,6-Dimethylpyrimidyl	287	SR	73	C ₃₆ H ₂₇ O ₆ N ₈ S	(+)	(-)
12.	2,6-Dimethoxypyrimidyl	260	SR	69	C ₃₈ H ₂₉ O ₈ N ₈ S	(++)	(+)
13.	5-Methyl-1,3,4-thiadiazolyl	292	R	75	C ₃₄ H ₂₄ O ₆ N ₈ S ₂	(+++)	(+)

D=dark ; F=flakes ; N=needles ; O=orange ; R=red ; S=Shining.

There was good agreement between the percentages of C and H found and required.

- The antibacterial properties were studied at two different concentrations of 500 μ g/ml and 1000 μ g/ml and the results with the dilution of 500 μ g/ml have been entered in the Tables.
- Diameters of the zones of inhibition against the control were measured and the difference upto 0.2 cm. represents the value obtained for every (+); (-) indicates no activity.

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